

mosaic

MOSAIC co-creation methodology toolkit

Section 3: The Gathering.

Authors: Marzia Mazzonetto, Maria Zolotonosa , Carmen Fenollosa, Fabien Lambert (Stickydot srl); Angela Simone, Anna Pellizzone, Federica Manzoli (Bassetti Foundation); Mélanie Marcel (Soscience).

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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1. The Gathering – guidelines for facilitation

You can either run the Gathering over one or two days, depending on the context.

If you decide to go for one day, in second part you can decide to skip the phases “Getting to know each other” (beginning of Part 2 in this guideline).

Objectives of the Gathering

- To bring together for the first time all selected participants and the organising team.
- For participants, to get to know each other and better understand each other’s expertise, experiences, needs and ideas.
- To further assess stakeholders’ views on the challenge and facilitate activities that will lead them to identify common ground and shared ideas.
- To form 3 groups (co-creation teams) that will be working separately on ideas and potential solutions to address the specific challenge.
- To kick-off of the co-creation work.

Structure

PART 1 (3 to 4 hours)

00:00-00:20 Welcome and introduction

Quick icebreaker: the lead facilitator, without introducing herself/himself, asks the participants to say one word they associate with the topic of the challenge – words are introduced in a Sli.do by a notetaker in real time, forming a word cloud that is projected on a screen. Brief introduction about the challenge, the aims of the co-creation process and timeline and explanation of the framework (how we will work together) and code of conduct.

00:20-01:00 Contextualisation

Short pitches by external speakers aimed at providing a brief, neutral introduction on existing data, studies, geographic data, etc. regarding the challenge topic. Pitches in the case of the MOSAIC pilot cities also focused on making more explicit the links between how the co-creation process can contribute to the city priorities (e.g., its Climate City Contract).

01:00-02:00 Barriers and concerns (*this part can be skipped in case of limited time availability*)

Exercise 1: participants are provided with an A3 hand-out and invited to draw on it following a topic specific question. Participants are then invited one by one to explain what they have been drawing to the rest of the group. This exercise is aimed at breaking the ice and getting participants to focus on the challenge topic. It is also helpful to get an understanding of their current habits around the topic.

Exercise 2: participants are asked to think about challenges / barriers / concerns they encounter, feel or perceive in relation to the topic of the co-creation. They are given a few minutes to write on post-its. The facilitator then asks them to share what they wrote, and clusters post-its on a flip chart.

02:00-02:15 Break

02:15-03:00 Visions and opportunities

Exercise 3: Participants are asked to focus on a question that makes them think about their vision of the future in relation to the challenge, and what changes are needed in order to get there. Example of a question: How will the city look like in 2030 in relation to the challenge? What will be the main observed transformations?

The facilitator explains that the co-creation project should contribute to shared desired objectives, and that these objectives can change and be revisited during the course of the programme.

Participants are invited to write their visions and expected transformations on post-its (one per post-it). The facilitator then asks them to share what they wrote, and clusters post-its on a flip chart.

03:00-03:20 Sharing of outcomes

A representative of each stakeholder group (ideally not the facilitators but a member of the group) shares main outcomes of exercise 2 (barriers and concerns) and exercise 3 (visions and opportunities).

3:20-3:30 Closing and introduction of Part 2

Part 2 (3 to 4 hours)

00:00-00:20 Welcome and recap

Welcome back and agenda of the day. Reminder of main outcomes of Part 1, highlighting potential common ground.

00:20-00:50 Getting to know each other – part 1 (*this part can be skipped in case of limited time availability*)

Activity: the off-line social network. Participants are invited to make a sketch of themselves on a piece of paper, write their name, and then stick the drawing on a big paper on a wall. Participants are then invited to split into pairs and have a few minutes to find at least one thing (possibly not work-related) that they share or have in common. They are invited to draw lines on the paper connecting their sketches in case they find something in common. The same process is repeated at least 4 or 5 times, depending on timing.

00:50-01:20 Getting to know each other – part 2 (*this part can be skipped in case of limited time availability*)

Activity: the crazy 6s. Participants are split into mixed-stakeholder groups (6 people per group). They are invited to think about crazy ideas related to the challenges. They are provided a hand-out where they are asked to very quickly draw one idea per minute (6 minutes in total for 6 ideas). Participants are then invited to share with the group their top two ideas, one by one.

01:20-01:35 Break

01:35-02:30 Forming groups

Participants are invited to write on a piece of paper an idea in relation to the challenge (i.e. solution, product, service). These should be formulated in the form of “My name is ... and my proposition is...”. The facilitator reminds participants about what already discussed so far, and previous exercises. The papers are then stuck to a white wall. Each participant is invited to briefly share their idea with the group. Not all participants have to make a proposition, the facilitator explains that it is ok not to have one.

The facilitator clusters ideas as much as possible, with the aim to try and reduce them to three groups. If not possible, the facilitators give three stickydots to each participant and asks them to vote for their three favourite propositions (or clusters of propositions). Only the three top voted propositions are used in the next steps (the other propositions are kept for potential use in the future, in case one of the top-three ones does not move forward).

Participants are invited to go stand next to the proposition out of the three that they would like the most to work on in the future. Three groups form. The facilitators invited them to look at the colour of their badges, and check whether all four colours are more or less equally represented in their group. If not, participants are invited to kindly move to their second favourite proposition, explaining that groups have to be balanced and inviting them to be collaborative and volunteer to move if needed. Working groups are therefore shaped (ideally no more than 10 participants per group).

02:30-03:20

The three groups are invited to gather and sit separately (one facilitator per group). The groups are provided with a template of points they have to work together on:

- (20 minutes) discuss together the concept of their co-creation proposition that emerged in the previous exercise, explaining that it can evolve into something different than originally stated (the facilitator makes sure all voices are heard). When agreeing on a proposition, participants are invited to think and write in the template about its expected transformations (desired goals); the barriers/challenges/concerns it addresses; the envisioned solution (in a very draft form); and a “wow sentence” about it (its starting/selling point).
- (20 minutes) groups are invited to plan how they want to work together. On the template, they fill together information on a) agreeing on at least one date to meet next; b) what are their needs in terms space, facilitation, tools, etc. c) distribution of roles and responsibilities; d) how to stay in touch (communication channels to be used).

03:20-03:30 Wrap-up and closing

2. Template for idea definition and planning further work (“Idea card”)

As a group you should try and agree on your initial idea. After this meeting you will get the chance to revisit the idea and even change it completely if needed. You have 20 minutes for this exercise.

Idea definition

<p>1. Challenge What challenge are you addressing?</p>	<p>2. Solution If the problem was solved, what would it look like?</p>
<p>3. Idea Describe your idea.</p>	<p>4. Value What is the unique selling point of your idea? What is its “wow” effect?</p>

Planning future work

<p>What roles are important to have in your team? Who can be in charge of what?</p>
<p>What are your needs in terms of meeting spaces, tools, further support?</p>
<p>What communication channel will you use to keep in touch? Who will set it up?</p>
<p>When will you meet next to advance the work?</p>
<p>How can we contact your team?</p>

3. Example of observation template

This template can be used by participants taking part in the Gathering as silent observers, to support the collecting observations.

Aims	
Aims of the observation	Please collect here information about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder views on the challenge. Differences in opinions and common ground. Group dynamics.
Topic	
Observer	Form filled in by:
Stakeholders	As far as you know: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How many participants took part in the event? Which stakeholder group was the largest/the smallest? What is your general view of the group? Were any important stakeholders / participants missing? Were the participants complementary to each other? Were they mostly aligned with peers from same stakeholder group? If not, can you briefly elaborate?
Atmosphere	Can you describe the atmosphere during the meeting in three key words? E.g., good / tensions / collaborative other... Can you briefly elaborate?
Evaluative questions	What went well? Please describe a situation (e.g., what, who, what were the outcomes, why do you think it went well?): What can be improved? How and why? Please describe: What remark or discussion comes to mind immediately? Please describe:
About the event	Can you describe a situation that stood out in a positive way? Please describe:
	Can you describe a situation that needs more attention next time? Please describe:
Dynamics of the engagement	Was there any common ground/common views/consensus that you noticed? Was there one or more contributions of a participant which stood out in a positive or negative way? Please describe:

	What was the (main) challenge the participants talked about during the event?
Suggestions	What suggestion for improvement would you – as an observer – give for the next steps?
Summary	Can you provide a short summary of the event with help of a few keywords or sentences?

4. Example of evaluation questionnaire

Thank you for your participation in The Gathering. To help us analyze our practices and improve future activities, please answer these few questions.

What is the color of your badge? (*each stakeholder group has been previously assigned a colour*)

Blue Red Yellow Green

On a scale of 1-10 (1 being the lowest and 10 being the highest) ...

1- How satisfied are you with what you gained (either personally, as an institution or as resulting impact) in this gathering?

2- Do you consider your time was well-spent by participating?

3- Do you feel your concerns were treated fairly compared to concerns of other participants?

4- Following The Gathering, do you think you have a better understanding of the concerns of other stakeholders (e.g. private actors, citizens, civil servants, etc.)?

5- Following The Gathering, did you include other type of participants' (e.g. private actors, citizens, civil servants, etc.) point of view to inform your perspective on the topic?

6- When you had divergent opinions, do you feel that the process helped you address these conflicts?

5. Example of privacy policy form

Privacy Policy (according to Articles 13 and 14 EU Regulation 679/2016, "Regulation")

Data controller

(name and address of entity), in its capacity as Data Controller (hereinafter '...') by virtue of its role as co-implementer of the ... process in activities in cooperation with the ..., agrees to protect the privacy of those who provide their personal data through this notice ('Notice').

In general, all information provided by you will be processed by ... in a lawful, fair and transparent manner. To this end, and as further described below, ... takes into consideration internationally recognised principles governing the processing of Personal Data, such as purpose limitation, storage space limitation, data minimisation, data quality and confidentiality.

For more details about the processing of your Personal Data, please see the Extended Privacy Policy at: ...

In addition, you may write to: ...

Types of data subject to processing

The personal data processed by ... are first name, last name, contact details (...).

Purpose, optionality and legal basis of data processing

The personal data described above will be processed for the following purposes: ...

- a) Activities related to participation in the InformAria co-creation and social research project in collaboration with the Municipality of Milan in the context of ..;
- b) fulfilment of the obligations laid down in laws, regulations and EU legislation, as well as provisions issued by authorities empowered to do so by law and by supervisory and control bodies ("compliance").

The processing of personal data for the purposes described above is always optional but, in the absence of consent, ... will not be able to fulfil any of these purposes.

For the purposes of participation in the in-person and online meetings of the ... process (letter a of this information notice), this purpose also includes the publication of the images/recordings of the participants during the workshops (the setting up and use of which is to be considered free of charge) for the sole purpose of documenting the events themselves and their possible dissemination via the web in ...'s internet and social accounts and through communication channels connected with the ... process. The legal basis for the aforementioned purpose is consent (Art. 6 n.1 lett a GDPR).

For 'compliance' purposes (letter b of this notice), the legal basis for the processing is a legal obligation to which is subject.

Recipients and transfer of personal data

Personal data may be shared with:

- natural persons authorised by ... to process personal data after signing an authorisation agreement for the processing of personal data (e.g. employees, collaborators and system administrators of FGB);
- parties that typically act as data controllers (e.g. companies providing IT services, consultants, etc.).
- subjects, bodies or authorities to whom it is mandatory to communicate personal data due to legal provisions, orders of authorities with respect to compliance purposes (e.g. Authorities and Supervisory and Control Bodies).

... does not transfer your aforementioned personal data outside the European Economic Area.5. Personal data storage

The personal data provided for the purposes set out in point 3, letters a), b), will be stored by the data controller within the terms of the law, exclusively for the time required for the purposes indicated.

Rights that may be exercised by the data subject

You have the right to request from ..., at any time, access to, rectification or erasure of your personal data or to object to their processing. You also have the right to request the restriction of processing in the cases provided for by Article 18 of the Regulation, as well as to obtain in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format the data concerning you, in the cases provided for by Article 20 of the Regulation.

You may exercise these rights by writing to ... at the following address: ...

In any case, you always have the right to file a complaint with the competent supervisory authority (Personal Data Protection Authority), pursuant to Article 77 of the Regulation, if you believe that the processing of your data is contrary to the legislation in force.

Having read the above information, I, the undersigned:

(Name and Last name)

I consent to the processing of my personal data for purposes related to participation in the in-person and online meetings of the InformAria process within the ...

I do not consent to processing for purposes related to participation in the in-person and online meetings of the ... process as part of the ... process (in which case it will not be possible to participate in the events)

(Date)*

(Signature)*

* DATE AND SIGNATURE LEGIBLE

6. Examples of informed consent forms

EXAMPLE 1

Declaration of Data Protection and Informed Consent for participation in activities that are part of the ... co-creation process.

Description of the process: (....)

Name and contact details of the data controller ("study leader"): (..)

Type of Data collected

During the ... co-creation process personal data will be collected. This includes: your name, contact information (email, phone number), occupation, professional background, and your personal opinions. Furthermore, photos, as well as audio and video recordings of the sessions will be taken.

Participation in the pilot

Participation in this pilot requires multiple workshops and meetings of various duration. Two workshops take place on Further in person and online meetings and workshops are held between ..., for a maximum of ... activities. Risks of participation should be negligible, but it is always possible that sensitive opinions or confidential information could be shared inadvertently. Participation in the study is always voluntary: you may choose not to respond to any question or to discuss a particular topic, and you can terminate your participation at any time.

Usage of your Data

The data generated within this process (interview / focus group / workshop / forum / meeting / interview) will be used for This includes the processing for research purposes and dissemination activities as well as reporting on project progress to The data generated will also be used by ... to further support ideas that will emerge from the process.

Data Recipients

Data recipients are:

Processing and Storing of your Data

For the analysis of the co-creation process, audio-recording, note-taking and collection of written information through post-its and alike will be performed. Your data will be stored Due to requirements of ..., the data collected might be stored until up to ... years after the end of the process. When storing data, ... researchers will erase personal data such as phone numbers and emails. Processed anonymised person-specific data might become part of publications (including scientific papers) and other dissemination materials. In the ... co-creation activities, you will state personal opinions which might be critical for you to some extent. While your names and screenshots may be published, we will protect the anonymity of personal opinions. Therefore, any personal opinions will be anonymized so that no relation can be established to the personal data of the participant. In addition, you have the explicit right to not answer a specific question. Your data will not be sent to third parties. The sole purpose of storing your data is for research, dissemination and policy support.

Your rights

During the ... co-creation activities, you are always free to not answer a specific question or leave without any consequences. If you would like to address a question or an issue, please feel free to do so. Furthermore, you shall have the right to access, to rectify, to erase, to restrict the processing and the right to data portability as granted in GDPR Article 15 -22. In addition you have the right to object to the processing of your personal data. You can also withdraw your consent at any time, by contacting us without any consequences. The withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal. If you are of the opinion that your data is processed unlawfully, you have the right to file a complaint with the data protection authority. Upon request your local supervisory authority will provide you information on exercising your right according to Article 57(e) GDPR. In order to exercise your rights, please contact

Dissemination of Results

The data generated will be used for ... related research purposes in the field of co-creation and open innovation, and dissemination materials. This includes deliverables, publications, reports, booklets and commentaries, policy briefs, blog posts, web pages, social media, journal articles and books.

Code of Conduct

Participation in ... is meant to be as agreeable and pleasant as possible for all those involved. Therefore, all participants agree to respect the following rules:

- Racism and discrimination: racist comments, discrimination on the basis of sex, age, or disability, publication of racist or sexist pictures and insulting persons are strictly banned.
- ... may not be misused for political, religious or advertising purposes.
- Infringements of copyright laws are not permitted.
- All participants' conduct should always be appropriate and never offensive or deprecating.

Fair rewarding

By taking part in the ... co-creation process, participants agree to respect the Ethical Guidelines These guidelines can be found below. A printed copy of the Ethical Guidelines is available upon registration. It can also be requested by email by sending a message to

Consent

After having stated these general conditions and rules, we are looking forward to a good cooperation and positive project results. We would like to thank you in advance for your participation in the project. The undersigned declare that they understand and consent to the conditions and rules of Both parties receive a copy of this declaration of consent.

I hereby release ... and any of its associated or affiliated institutions, their directors, officers, agents, employees and customers from all claims of every kind on account of such use.

Participant's name :

Contact's name:

Participant's signature:

Contact's signature:

Location, day/month/year

Location, day/month/year

EXAMPLE 2

You have been invited to participate in the ... co-creation (participatory innovation) process, which will take place - both face-to-face and online - between (... add start and end date), as part of the social research project / co-creation process

A co-creation process involves actors from different fields (business, associations, research and governance) working together, sharing their experiences, skills and points of view in order to develop a concrete solution capable of responding to a common challenge. In this specific case, through your participation, you will help us to develop (...).

The process will take place over several meetings, some of which will be audio-recorded so that the conversations between you and the other participants can be transcribed and analysed at a later date for the sole purposes of the ... project.

The transcripts of the dialogues that will take place and the ideas that will emerge will not contain your name. The results of this process, as well as being used to develop a solution to (...), may be used for scientific publication in aggregate form; therefore, the contributions of (individual) people will not be identifiable.

Furthermore, in order to protect the confidentiality of the participants, by consenting to participate, you agree to ensure that the content of the discussions that will take place during the meetings in which you will participate will not be shared in any way with parties who were not involved. The same will apply to all participants.

Your participation is voluntary. Please feel free to withdraw from the process at any time. Should you decide to withdraw from the process, it will not be possible to remove any contributions you may have made before withdrawing.

Through this informed consent form, you have received complete and truthful information about this research project and its aims.

By participating in ...'s in-presence and online meetings you agree to take part in the co-creation and social research process described above.

Your participation is free of charge. The intellectual property of the proposals that will be conceived and potentially realised, even outside the (...) project process, remains exclusively in the hands of the creators (members of the working groups) and is not patentable. While it remains shared between the members of the working groups, further reflections on the intellectual property of the solutions developed and how to recognise each member's contribution can be carried out by the participants themselves during the process.

Signature (legible)

Date (legible)

7. Example of ethical guidelines on fair engagement processes

- No co-creation process should be set up without a prior shared reflection on intellectual property rights and the potential profits distribution of its outputs. Especially in negotiating with private sector representatives their participation in the process, this element should be highlighted and discussed before the start of the co-creation path. The involvement of the private sector in co-creation processes represents both a challenge (e.g., in case of unfair appropriation of shared ideas) and an opportunity. Having representatives of the private sector involved from the start should be mediated by co-creation initiators by fostering an open conversation on potential rewards that can be acceptable to them.
- The definition of intellectual property rights and potential profits distribution can be achieved through a top-down process (i.e. the public administration running the processes defines and informs participants about what is achievable and whom it belongs to) or, even better, a bottom-up approach (i.e. all participants are involved in the definition of rewarding expectations, ahead of the start of the process).
- Public administrations often dispose of entire units/departments dedicated to managing and strengthening the collaboration with (and governance of) the private sector. It is advisable to involve representatives of such offices in co-creation processes. They can both support the exploitation of co-creation ideas through city-owned channels (e.g. business incubators) and mediate discussions on ownership issues with private companies involved in the process. With them, while looking at sectors in which this kind of discussion is gaining momentum (open data), explore a new way of reconfiguring products and services for the public good as “public products”, focusing less on who are the idea/products conception holders and more on the purposes for which the product can be used.
- Creative commons forms of ownership are ideal, even though only sometimes possible. Shared ownership of outcomes should always be preferred. When not possible, due to the need to privatise innovative ideas, other forms of reward should be adopted, such for example shareholding or free access to products and services for those who contributed to their development.
- Transparency is key. Whether any form of reward is considered or not, it is important to inform participants from the start about the conditions of their participation in the process. This should be clearly stated in informed consent forms and explained to them.
- Communication actions to inform co-creation participants on how their contribution has been used and finalised is of utmost importance. While planning a co-creation process, define means and channels for follow-up activities.